

Academic Review on the Effect of the Pandemic on Social Relationships in Educational Children

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Abstract

Because of the breakout of a pandemic on a global scale, families were forced to swiftly adjust to the shift to schooling through distant learning. During the COVID-19 epidemic, 93 percent of homes with children of school age have taken part in at least one kind of social distance learning, and the majority of these households are currently participating in at least one form of distance learning. Together, a parent and kid engage in the activity of distance learning via the use of a computer. The shift has been difficult for a variety of families in many different situations. Accessibility difficulties disproportionately affected low-income families since these families may not have access to the two components that are essential for distance education. These components include a computer and a high-speed internet connection. As a result of the epidemic, children were forced to take part in remote school, and many developed antisocial tendencies. It used to be that the children who lived in the village would engage in play and share, but it is now quite clear that these youngsters do not have the

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chance to do any of those things. It is true that children are becoming more antisocial because of the epidemic, especially when we consider the fact that children from other households are not sharing their games. Because of this condition, both school life and the jobs of teachers and administrators are placed in very precarious positions. The administrations of the schools have various responsibilities with reference to these issues. It is possible to find a solution to this issue by enlisting the aid of sociologists and psychologists working at academic institutions. There are 13.5 million young people between the ages of 5 and 17 who do not have access to these technologies, as shown by a research that was released by the NEA. Families also found it difficult to understand how the education and development of their children affect all the dynamics of the family when the children took part in distance learning programs. Now that teachers and parents have had some time to adjust to the disruption caused by the virus, both the benefits and the drawbacks of the epidemic are starting to become clearer.

Keywords: *Teaching in the Pandemic Process, Learning in the Pandemic Process, Distance Education and Pandemic, Pandemic Effect in Education and Training, Effect of the Pandemic on Social Relations*

1. Introduction

Most students believe that they are receiving a quality education, although they are under pressure from a variety of academic, emotional, financial, and health-related stressors, as the results of a study that was conducted jointly by International Education Associations and Specialist Institutions found. Many studies have been conducted by National Parent-Teacher Institutions to investigate the impact of education received at a distance. It is not yet clear, particularly to teachers and educators, how pupils will be affected by this circumstance. The struggles of the parents are still passed down to the children, and those struggles have the same ongoing impact. 65 percent of parents are worried about the chance that their kid would fall behind academically as a result of school disruptions or usage of an illegal substance. These worries are not without foundation. Because of the pandemic, children's exposure to remote schooling has led to the development of asocial personalities among these youngsters. In the past, the children who lived in the village would play games together and join in

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the fun, which was beneficial to both their social development and the growth of their personalities. It is fair to conclude that these opportunities are no longer available to them. On the other side, it has been seen that children from homes who have a higher degree of economic welfare are more asocial in response to the epidemic. This is since in the past, there was no such thing as sharing games. Because of this condition, both school life and the jobs of teachers and administrators are placed in very precarious positions. In relation to these issues, the administration of the school could manage certain responsibilities. Once again, it is possible to find a solution to this issue by enlisting the aid of sociologists and psychologists working at academic institutions.

A staggering 63 percent of parents are worried about the amount of time their children spend in front of electronic gadgets. At the same time, sixty percent of parents are worried that as their children become older, they won't be able to maintain the same number of social ties as they had before they had children. The fact that 59% of parents are worried about the mental health of their children is an added problem worth mentioning. Some of the elements that may influence the educational results of distance learning include a student's individual learning style, the learning environment in which they are immersed, and the level of participation that the student's parents have in their child's education. It is a fact that students find it difficult to move away from the organized setting of the classroom for a variety of reasons, and one of the most prevalent of these reasons is based on the disparity that exists in digital media. Young people who do not have access to a dependable high-speed internet connection and a gadget that can be used for one-on-one distance learning have the greatest amount of difficulty. Without these resources, it is impossible to have a pleasant experience with distance learning; yet, sadly, millions of students do not have access to these tools. There are many youngsters who are putting out their best effort in an environment that adheres to a schedule that is quite regimented and consistent. When they are in the comfort of their own homes, these pupils could be more easily sidetracked. The fact that they are unable to hand in their assignments or attend the class is an illustration of one of the challenges that may have a negative impact on their ability to get an education via online courses.

2. Decreased Interaction

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Most parents now enroll their children in classes that can be completed online while they are at work. It may be extremely challenging for these families to supply the same level of nourishment for their children at home as is supplied for them at school. Many students discover that it is challenging to compensate for the lack of face-to-face connection with their professors and classmates when they are taking part in an educational program that is delivered through remote learning. It is possible for instructors to have difficulties differentiating between pupils who are engaged in the work at hand and those who are looking for further aid when both groups of students are in the classroom at the same time. Students who are uninterested in the topic at hand are statistically less likely to engage in remote classroom discussions. A gathering that is attended by no students at all is statistically more likely to be unproductive and silent. The decline in the child's sociability is strongly tied to these concerns, which is something that is concerning for both teachers and parents. A lot of people are confused about how this might result in long-term improvements in the classroom after the students come back. Even while this is the case for the children who are attending school in the city, the children who were raised in the village did not have a significantly distinct experience in terms of their education or their socialization.

Students who struggle to concentrate or who suffer from anxiety may discover that they do better when they are at home. Students who have trouble attending or responding questions in class may find that taking part online is a more comfortable experience for them than being there in person. Students who had improved their ability to self-regulate were better able to work independently because they were better able to follow their schedule, remember what time their meeting was, schedule time to focus on their projects throughout the day, and better track deadlines for their work. This allowed students to work more independently than before.

3. More Sleep

Another advantage is that kids often get more sleep because of the change. The fact that children can get more rest is one of the many benefits that comes along with educating them remotely. This, in turn, leads to an improvement in the academic performance of the children. When children attend a traditional classroom setting, they learn a great deal more than just reading and math; in addition, they

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develop fundamental social and emotional competencies that will serve them well long into adulthood. The shift toward education delivered over the internet may have a variety of implications on children, including how it may influence their level of academic success. There are valid grounds for parents to be worried about the possible impacts on their children's psychological and social development. These effects might be caused by exposure to the substance. When seen through the lenses of sociologists and psychologists, this appears to provide a contrast to the concept of asociality. In other words, even though students have been hurt in a variety of ways because of remote education, this problem might be seen as a benefit. However, the fact that this problem is the root cause of the child's lack of socialization should not be overlooked.

4. Society's Progress

It is impossible for students to achieve the same level of social development through distance learning because they miss the opportunities to interact with their classmates and teachers. Concerned about the quality of the education their children are receiving, an increasing number of parents are opting to instruct their children at home or engaging in other forms of independent work.

Many parents report that their children are either absent from school or spend their time playing video games instead of doing the homework assigned to them.

The ability to interact with other students was, without a doubt, the highlight of the academic experience for most of the pupils. If these pupils do not have any social ties, it may be challenging for them to supply any type of attention to the class. Students may have difficulty understanding and conveying their feelings via the use of remote video platforms, which might be yet another obstacle for them. Many parents are concerned that their children may fall behind in their schooling and become socially isolated if they choose to continue their education at home. Although many parents have tried to restrict the amount of time their children spend in front of electronic media, some adolescents may now have to spend several hours each day on the computer at school, with minimal interaction with other people. When there are insufficient chances for pupils to interact with one another in a one-on-one setting, it is particularly challenging for younger kids to develop their social

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skills. A person's ability to have good relationships with the people and things around them might make that person feel more driven.

Children may find themselves more motivated to learn when they take part in collaborative activities like class projects or presentations, or even when they just contribute to classroom discussions. They are not able to keep up this level of driving when they must work alone. It's possible that some students may see the fact that they won't be subjected to the same kind of peer pressure when they participate in distant learning as a good component of the format. While some students find the social aspects of the classroom to be a welcome diversion, others find it to be a setting that increases their anxiety. Many pupils have been able to achieve success throughout their time spent working remotely since they are not subject to the social pressure of being physically present at a school. Children who, for instance, may have been the object of bullying at school have discovered that taking part in distant learning is a welcome reprieve. It should come as no surprise that sociality and asociality are connected to this topic. The management of the school handles certain responsibilities right now. Other children may feel a sense of relief when they are relieved of the pressure of looking good or meeting certain social norms, and children who are shy or anxious may find it easier to approach teachers for aid when they need it. While this is especially true for children who have access to the Internet at home, it may also be the case that other children feel a sense of relief.

If students have fewer possibilities to engage in extracurricular activities outside of the classroom, such as joining clubs or sports teams, they are more likely to focus on their academic work and develop better study habits. Even more so than before, it is now abundantly clear how fundamentally crucial the notion of "being social" is to the growth of the kid.

5. Concerns About Emotions

What kinds of mental and emotional changes might we expect to see in a kid who attends school online? This is a huge worry shared by a lot of different parents. A potential emotional toll may be exacted on children because of the unpredictability and disruption brought on by the pandemic, in addition to the impending relocation of the next distance education location. University psychologists and sociologists play a pivotal role in this respect. [Citation needed] Following the pandemic, it is

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essential for the administrations of schools to comment and make observations about the state of the students. Because there are certain activities that can be conducted by the requirements of school administrations, and these activities can reveal and decide the accumulated potential, asociality or sociability tendencies in children.

There are many youngsters who are putting out their best effort in an environment that adheres to a schedule that is quite regimented and consistent. When they are at home, it is probable that these pupils may get more easily distracted. Because of a choice that can have a negative impact on their online education, they are unable to either give their work or continue with the course. Most parents now enroll their children in classes that can be completed online while they are at work. It may be challenging for these families to provide their children the same things they get at school when they are with them at home.

6. Decreased Interaction

What is meant by the concept of "reduced interaction" is to highlight the concept of sociality of the child who has received distance education and to emphasize how to cut the possibility of asociality. In other words, what is meant by the concept of "reduced interaction" is to highlight how to cut the possibility of asociality. Many students have found it difficult to compensate for the loss of face-to-face interaction with their instructors and other students when they must do their coursework online. It is possible for instructors to have difficulties differentiating between pupils who are engaged in the work at hand and those who are looking for further aid when both groups of students are in the classroom at the same time. Students who are uninterested in the topic at hand are statistically less likely to engage in remote classroom discussions. A gathering that is attended by no students at all is statistically more likely to be unproductive and silent.

Taking classes via online learning may aid us in keeping a healthy balance between our academic, career, and familial responsibilities. Students are given access to information and learning opportunities that make academic progression simple and straightforward. On the other hand, we are all conscious of the fact that we have a responsibility to our pupils to make certain that the education they get is correct. This is since conventional and online forms of education will unavoidably merge

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at some time in the not-too-distant future. The pandemic that was brought on by the COVID-19 virus has had several distinct and varied consequences on the educational system in every region of the globe. Some nations, in reaction to the virus, have created containment measures, such as social distance restrictions and lockdown procedures (Korkmaz and Toraman, 2020). Schools were among the first institutions to follow government requirements and put containment strategies into effect, which included replacing conventional methods of face-to-face instruction with means of distant learning. To stop the spread of contagious illnesses, this measure was taken. Various students were able to profit from distance learning despite the many obstacles connected with inadequate infrastructure and technological equipment, such as access to laptops or computers. This was the case even though there was a lack of both (Ferri et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2021).

During times when schools were forced to lock their doors for reasons related to safety, a variety of strategies were implemented to keep pupils engaged in instructional activities. However, despite the significant strides that schools are taking to keep children's learning, many academics argue that distance learning does not equip young students with the emotional and social skills that are necessary for their development. This is the case even though schools are making these important strides. This is even though schools are taking significant measures to ensure the continued education of students (Dong et al., 2020). Additionally, Bransen et al. (2020) and Tham et al. (2021) argue that digital learning models do not allow students to conceptualize sociocultural concepts and develop social skills that are critical to their academic processes. ("Distance education and the social literacy of elementary school ... - Cell") This is even though digital learning models emphasize abstract concepts to provide students with basic theoretical skills. (Cell: "Distance education and the social literacy of primary school students... - Cell") Regarding these same matters, it is essential to emphasize how important it is for school administrations to have the help of academics trained in the fields of psychology and sociology from local universities.

A fundamental level of social literacy ought to be a prerequisite for participation in any kind of educational program for young people. It forms the student's ability in the literacy skills learned via social interactions with other children and adults, whether those interactions take place within or outside of a formal or informal curriculum. This extends beyond the student's ability to read or write. These exchanges may take place either within or outside of a traditional classroom environment (Blair

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et al., 2018). Children can build their social literacy, as said by Kirova and Jamison (2018), via interactions with themselves, their instructors, their families, their classmates, and even with other people with whom they do not engage one-on-one. [Citation needed] In addition, O'Byrne and colleagues (2018) argue that children should acquire social literacy via conversation with their friends and families, beginning at a young age and focusing on the subject of the average family. This should take place within the setting of the typical family.

With online education, schools can have a far lower student-to-teacher ratio than they would in a conventional classroom environment. This technique raises each student's attention level and assures that all students communicate equally with educators and each other on the remote platform, so eradicating all obstacles to communication that may have existed before. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) and Vedder-Weiss et al. (2019), pupils in elementary schools who take part in distant learning increase the professional links that exist between children of the same generation. Nevertheless, comprehensive social literacy initiatives have been unsuccessful because of a lack of cross-party participation or connection. This is the case despite tries to enhance learning and interaction on virtual platforms. When it comes to efficiently teaching social literacy to primary school students via the use of distance learning, there are a few obstacles that need to be cleared away first. Because of the restricted infrastructure that is accessible to them, including limited access to computers and laptops, many students are unable to use virtual platforms for their education (Zhu et al., 2020). The fact that children come from a variety of socioeconomic circumstances, and the reality that some children are raised at home in environments that are more favorable to constructive learning than others, both serve to further complicate this issue. Even though the socialization or asociality of the students in terms of socio-economic balances revealed many gaps in the pandemic, it is a fact that the authorities that should intervene in this situation are the school administrations. This is because school administrations are the ones who oversee the schools.

Because online learning occurs within the framework of assigned tasks, it might be challenging to keep one's attention on the subject matter that is being delivered (Zhu et al., 2020). Children have a more tough time developing the skills essential for social literacy and interacting with their peers when they are separated by a greater distance. This is because of this aspect. Students in elementary school get the benefits of social literacy because it inspires them to take part in activities that involve

collaboration with their peers. According to Teo and Divakar (2021), social literacy provides children in elementary school with the potential to not only build students' social and people skills, but also to engage in cooperative learning, which is crucial for academic growth. [Citation needed] In addition, instructors play an essential part in aiding students in the development of skills like as leadership and negotiation, which are important for students to successfully navigate the problems they meet while learning (Zhu et al., 2020). According to Wang et al. (2018), social literacy provides primary school children with the capacity to recognize their own talents and to engage in group projects or forum discussions that are offered by their teachers. According to Teo and Divakar (2021), peer mediation is a basic technique to problem-solving that helps kids in elementary school manage disputes and achieve integration in the classroom. This is because peer mediation is a kind of peer mediation. Peer mediation is a strategy for conflict management that, according to Teo and Divakar, may be taught to pupils in elementary school by their instructors (Ay et al., 2019). Because of this condition, school administrations are going to need to conduct careful monitoring and intervention by the recommendations of sociologists and psychologists from academic institutions, particularly after the pandemic.

Students in primary school are taught the importance of social literacy via these types of programs, which also help them develop the cognitive and soft skills that are essential for best academic growth. Students who engage in social learning develop the necessary self-confidence to take part in conflict resolution with a peer mediator in an environment that is private, confidential, and risk-free; this leads to a society that is more peaceful.

Students in a primary school that makes excellent use of online education may see an increase for engagement that occurs between one another. Additionally, the method cuts several structural biases, such as variations in regional dialects, chromatic aberrations, and deviations in the method's structure. Therefore, in contrast to the impersonal nature of face-to-face learning, which does not support the development of social literacy, remote learning does.

7. Theoretical Fundamentals

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The advocates of the social learning theory contend that students can absorb information more efficiently when they engage in conversation with one another, watch one another, and take part in many other types of directed communication (Heslop & Meredith, 2020). Albert Bandura, a psychologist, proposed this theory in the early 1960s, suggesting that the success of kids in school is dependent on their engagement in a variety of social activities and experiences (Heslop & Meredith, 2020). As a result, a platform for distance learning that is well-structured should make it possible for students to develop social cognition by taking part in a distance learning community and to collaborate with their classmates to construct knowledge through participation in distance discussion forums (Huang et al., 2020). When primary school instructors encourage their pupils to engage in group discussions and other academic activities, students who are enrolled in distance education programs based on social learning ideas experience increases in their levels of social literacy (Li et al., 2020; Martin & Bolliger, 2018).

For instance, one educator found that students' social literacy abilities declined somewhat when they were unable to engage in remote education because they lacked access to the essential hardware or software. This prevented the students from engaging in the learning experience. It is a fact that you are unable to engage in fruitful discussion with other people, take part in activities on a variety of distant platforms, or effectively understand what they are trying to convey to you. The following is an example of the interview question that was asked, which led to the identification of the second part as teachers:

"The issue of what variables are effective in primary school teachers' development of their students' social literacy through distance education during Covid-19 consists of two basic ideas:

- *Adaptations to existing teaching methods and flexible learning opportunities.*

Distance education also needed changes in the methods used to enable students to learn the importance of social literacy skills. In addition, one of them said that they had to change their teaching methods because they could not apply it with distance education. For example, due to the nature of distance education, role playing practice among students has been made impossible; as a result, our ability to properly ease children's relationships has been adversely affected.

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- *In addition, we could not organize activities for students to work in groups, which meant that students were not able to develop their ability to collaborate effectively.*

For example, when comparing their pre- and post-pandemic experiences, the instructors found that students were more attentive to the subject they were studying when they took part in distance learning. Those who saw this change said that the students appeared more interested in the learning process and their attention levels increased. Additionally, many of the educators said that the connection between student, family and educator has improved because of the student completing their education completely remotely. Some of the lecturers said that in the past, students used their digital technology skills mostly for pleasure, but now they can turn these skills into distance learning. In addition, according to some educators, children who took part in distance education within the scope of the Covid-19 project had the opportunity to connect with their teachers and classmates in a virtual environment, different from face-to-face communication.

8. In addition to providing students with social literacy skills, to be able to prevent asociality by encouraging them to be social

The emotional issues that occur because of the challenges students experience because of the difficulties caused by the distance education system, which limits the development of social literacy skills, may be addressed by the engagement of the student's parents in the learning process. Teachers were also able to equip pupils with social literacy skills via the use of online education since it allowed them to approach students on an individual basis throughout the epidemic. This was made possible since most of the children were in settings that were comfortable for them, namely their homes. As a result, it is now much simpler for educators to train kids in newly developed abilities associated with social literacy, skills which the students will ultimately be able to put to use (George et al., 2021; Tzifopoulos, 2020). In the same context, instructors can impart social literacy skills to their pupils via the implementation of an implicit curriculum and the use of indirect teaching methods (Alsubaie, 2015). It is possible that it has been proved that the use of distant learning platforms increases students' self-control, regulation, motivation, and supervision. These results and conclusions are based on the experiences of the instructors who took part in the study. In addition, students were unable to extend

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their self-control to the point where they could manage their emotions; nevertheless, Dong et al. (2020) said that distance learning did not prepare young learners with the emotional and social skills necessary for success. On the other side, the findings of this study showed that young students may improve their ability to regulate their emotions via the use of remote learning. However, to make this a reality, it is essential that both parents and teachers collaborate. Alsubaie (2018) emphasized the need of parental engagement in their children's education, particularly in reading, to aid their children's academic achievement. Because of the unique characteristics of distance education programs, instructors must adapt their pedagogical approaches as well as the course materials they use. According to the findings of the research conducted, educators value having greater autonomy in remote classes. This conclusion was validated by Huang et al. (2020), who also suggested that instructors should be flexible in their instructional approaches, as well as the materials, resources, and methods they use to educate students, as well as the ways in which they adapt to new learning systems. In the context of this discussion, flexibility is beneficial to educators because it enables them to adapt innovative solutions to solve the problems given by remote learning. Because of this, they can effectively send the relevant information and abilities (Burgess & Sievertsen, 2020). Alawamleh et al. (2020), Kaufman (2021), and Mitchell (2020) concluded that distance learning is the same as face-to-face communication in that it eases bonding and knowledge sharing and creates a sense of community. Flexible learning opportunities are in line with these findings, making them consistent with the conclusions of these researchers. Therefore, instructors who are familiar with how to use various technologies for distance learning may use these tools to aid in molding and enhancing the social literacy abilities of their pupils. As a result, digital literacy is an important problem that must be solved, and all individuals associated with educational institutions should have it (Johnson et al., 2021; Lytras et al., 2021).

The use of technologies that make communication more focused is one way in which educators may help to the growth of students' social literacy within the communities of their classrooms (Kozak & Recchia, 2019; Wright & Domke, 2019). According to Pinto and Leite (2020), social literacy may be increased in the classroom when teachers make use of classroom discussion boards, social tagging, video blogs, wikis, and podcasts. This is the conclusion reached by the researchers. During the pandemic that has engulfed the whole globe, many educational institutions have shifted their focus to

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distant learning, which comes replete with interactive components such as online discussion forums. Students improve their ability to engage with other people by buying the skills necessary to accurately understand messages and reply in an acceptable manner while using various online platforms. It is the responsibility of teachers to create an environment in the classroom that promotes active engagement from students as well as the sharing of ideas and personal anecdotes (Karakas & Kartal, 2020).

Exposing primary school pupils to a range of social circumstances and providing them with the chance to communicate afterwards about how they are feeling are both effortless ways to ease the development of an environment that is favorable to the learning of social literacy. Children who are raised in such surroundings realize the significance of social ties, which leads to them developing a feeling of self-assurance and responsibility via their interactions with their peers as they grow older. On the other hand, the principles of distant digital learning hinder face-to-face interactions and do not fully impart social literacy. In a classroom setting for students in elementary school, it is vital for the teacher to play the role of principal facilitator of learning. The research conducted by Onyema et al. (2019) proves that teachers play an important part in fostering social literacy in students who are enrolled in distant learning programs. To educate students how to be socially literate, teachers need to examine the significance of social signals in daily encounters. These signals include things like eye gaze, facial expression, verbal tone, and body language. According to Heljakka and Ihamaki (2018), this not only boosts the amount of engagement, but it also enables pupils to notice other non-verbal components of a conversation being had. In addition, teachers need to prove to their classes the correct method for pupils to interact with one another by having them rehearse and act out different scenarios. Students have the potential to create wonderful connections with their peers and increase their self-confidence by using these tactics, which allow them the chance to do so.

Learning that takes place outside of the typical classroom environment may be aided using a wide variety of technology-based software, hardware, and other resources. This kind of learning can help individuals improve their social literacy and educational credentials. The ability of students to use computer-assisted learning and to navigate many apps to engage with their instructors and classmates was essential to the success of the remote education program that was introduced during the Covid-19 epidemic (Bond, 2020; Brina & Delahunty, 2021). When it comes to taking part in distant learning, both primary school pupils and lecturers meet several challenges, as was shown in several studies.

However, education and curriculum academics are increasingly bringing attention to the absence of practical means for students in elementary school to buy and take part with social literacy using video-linked learning platforms. To provide kids in primary school with the knowledge and abilities needed for social literacy, it is vital for the home and school environments to work together. However, trainers play an extremely important part in setting up the validity of the ideas that underpin this profession (Bond, 2020).

For students to be able to take an active role in the learning process, instructors of elementary school children need to work with their students to improve their listening skills. In a similar vein, Brina and Delahunty (2021) believe that instructors should educate students to create partnerships in the learning environment, and that students should learn to talk to and listen to each other during activities. Both points are supported by the evidence. Students also need to be taught that instructors have a responsibility to instruct students on how to form partnerships inside the classroom setting. They should take the time to congratulate one another on their own accomplishments and question one another. Students in elementary school get a sense of self-assurance from taking part in projects of this kind, which also contribute significantly to their social literacy. Because of this, teachers at elementary schools ought to provide their students with opportunities to work together and cooperate with their classmates, or to construct a community in the classroom that is founded on partnerships with one another. In addition, instructors at elementary schools shouldn't deliberately pair up kids with friends or classmates; rather, they should offer pupils the autonomy to choose these relationships on their own will (Schreuder & Savitz, 2020). Pupils are given the option to pick partners with whom they have shared interests and to form friendships; it is crucial for students to be successful in achieving their academic aims. This topic has a strong connection to the process of socialization that a student goes through, regardless of whether they live in a metropolis or a countryside.

9. Making Meaningful Connections with Each Other

One of the most crucial parts of social learning is setting up meaningful connections with one another's experiences and perspectives. Children have trouble keeping these relationships since there is less face-to-face contact because of the move to remote learning. This causes the children to have difficulty

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sustaining these connections. One of the ways in which remote learning helps to contribute to the creation of an atmosphere that is identity-safe for primary school pupils is by removing some obstacles, such as elevated levels of poverty, a lack of equipment, or modest clothes such as uniforms (Chang et al. , 2019; Collins and Halverson, 2018). According to Tyagi et al research, 's students get the impression that remote platforms treat them with respect and that they are accepted and welcomed there. Therefore, initiatives such as these promote social literacy since they cut a considerable number of the preconceptions that are prominent in conventional classroom settings. Using distance education, schools can enroll a much smaller number of students in each class than they would in a typical classroom environment. This technique raises each student's attention level and assures that all students communicate equally with educators and each other on the remote platform, so eradicating all obstacles to communication that may have existed before. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) and Vedder-Weiss et al. (2019), pupils in elementary schools who take part in distant learning increase the professional links that exist between children of the same generation. Nevertheless, comprehensive social literacy initiatives have been unsuccessful because of a lack of cross-party participation or connection. This is the case despite tries to enhance learning and interaction on virtual platforms. When seen in this light, it is easy to see why it is very essential for the leadership of educational institutions to have the aid of sociologists and psychologists, particularly from academic institutions.

When it comes to efficiently teaching social literacy to primary school students via the use of distance learning, there are a few obstacles that need to be cleared away first. Because of the restricted infrastructure that is accessible to them, including limited access to computers and laptops, many students are unable to use virtual platforms for their education (Zhu et al., 2020). The fact that children come from a variety of socioeconomic circumstances, and the reality that some children are raised at home in environments that are more favorable to constructive learning than others, both serve to further complicate this issue. Because online learning occurs within the framework of assigned tasks, it might be challenging to keep one's attention on the subject matter that is being delivered (Zhu et al., 2020). Children have a more tough time developing the skills essential for social literacy and interacting with their peers when they are separated by a greater distance. This is because of this aspect.

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The difficulties met in teaching and developing social literacy skills can be summed up as "the difficulties you encountered while attempting to teach and develop social literacy skills to primary school students through distance learning during the Covid-19 pandemic." The interview topic that led to the development of this emphasis area was about the difficulties and problems that primary school kids experience when it comes to their social literacy abilities. The following are the three fundamental ideas that will be discussed in this issue:

1. *Problems caused by technology.*
2. *difficulties caused by society and*
3. *Aid provided by parents.*

During the Covid-19 pandemic, distance education also had significant benefits that attracted students' attention. In addition, because of the participation of students in distance education activities, their social literacy abilities were developed. These results showed that distance learning platforms can influence the future of relationships between educators, students, and parents, increasing children's overall academic achievement. According to Bond (2020), the aid provided by parents as their children attend distance courses was an approach to foster good connections between the three parties involved. Parental involvement in the learning process can address the emotional problems that arise because of the difficulties students face because of the distance education system that hinders the development of social literacy skills. In addition, teachers were able to provide students with social literacy skills through distance education, as they were able to reach students individually during the pandemic. This was possible because most of the children were in environments familiar to them, namely at home. Therefore, it has become easier for teachers to instruct students on new social literacy-related skills that they will eventually be able to use (George et al., 2021; Tzifopoulos, 2020). In the same scenario, educators can teach social literacy skills to their students by adopting an implicit curriculum and using indirect techniques (Alsubaie, 2015). The findings of this research may have proven, based on the experience of the participating instructors, that the use of distance learning platforms improves students' self-control, regulation, motivation, and supervision. Additionally, although students could not extend their self-control to regulate their emotions, Dong et al. (2020) said that distance learning does not equip young learners with emotional and social abilities.

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On the other side, the findings of this study showed that young students may improve their ability to regulate their emotions via the use of remote learning. However, to make this a reality, it is essential that both parents and teachers collaborate. Alsubaie (2018) emphasized the need of parental engagement in their children's education, particularly in reading, to aid their children's academic achievement. Because of the unique characteristics of distance education programs, instructors must adapt their pedagogical approaches as well as the course materials they use. According to the findings of the research conducted, educators value having greater autonomy in remote classes. This conclusion was supported by Huang et al. (2020), who also suggested that teachers should be flexible in their instructional tactics, as well as the learning materials and resources that they use and the ways in which they adapt to different learning systems. In the context of this discussion, flexibility is beneficial to educators as it lets them adapt new ways to solve the obstacles given by remote learning. Because of this, they can effectively send the relevant information and abilities (Burgess & Sievertsen, 2020). In addition, the findings of Alawamleh et al. may be paralleled with the implementation of flexible learning options. According to Kaufman (2021) and Mitchell (2020), remote learning has the same effects as face-to-face communication in that it fosters the formation of bonds, enables the exchange of information, and generates a feeling of community. Therefore, instructors who are familiar with how to use various technologies for distance learning may use these tools to aid in molding and enhancing the social literacy abilities of their pupils.

As a result, digital literacy is an important problem that must be solved, and all individuals associated with educational institutions should have it (Johnson et al., 2021; Lytras et al., 2021). One of the findings of this study was that pupils in elementary schools have uneven access to learning materials as well as technology and software for online learning. It was vital for students to have access to these technologies for them to absorb the content that was delivered in distant learning courses. The instructors recognized this gap as the root cause of the considerable social literacy ability gap that existed among their pupils. This was a significant problem, since it meant that a considerable number of students were unable to finish their educations through distance learning because they lacked access to the proper equipment and resources. Another piece of research came to the same result, namely, that not all students had an equal probability of buying academic material. This conclusion agrees with that finding. For their part, the trainers were unable to succeed in supplying universal access to

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distance learning since their individual skill sets varied (Ferri et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2020). Because of this inconsistency, students who lacked access to learning materials like the technology or software necessary for remote education were at a disadvantage (Bol, 2020), which had a negative impact on the literacy skills they had (UNESCO, 2020). The lack of information that the teachers had about technology and the remote education system was the most startling finding that came out of this investigation. It is of the utmost need to cultivate a culture of digital literacy among educators and students, particularly considering the Covid-19 epidemic (Hung et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2021; Kunzmann, 2020). Because of this, the attitudes of teachers suggested that access to digital learning equipment and resources had to be broadened among disadvantaged student groups to guarantee that all students can successfully take part in remote learning. They have been unable to buy the teacher-guided social literacy skills that are essential for their overall development in the areas of behavior, cognition, and academics because they do not have access to these resources.

10. Conclusion

There are receptive to all ideas, whether they pertain to the performing arts, the kitchen, the dance floor, or the stage. Some parents would have enrolled their children in distance learning classes as well, so that at the end of the year, the children would have not only learned structured knowledge, but also some soft skills. Because of the epidemic, youngsters have developed an antisocial personality because of their exposure to online schooling. Children who live in villages, as opposed to children who live in cities, do not have the chance to play together and partake in the activities of the past. On the other hand, the children of families living in the city who fall into the category of having high income levels did not have access to any activities, spaces, or even opportunities that included sharing. Due to the virus, these youngsters have grown considerably more antisocial than they were before, while already being at a key time in their development. Because of this condition, both school life and the jobs of teachers and administrators are placed in very precarious positions. At the same time, it places certain responsibilities on the administration of schools. For the academic community to be able to find a solution to this issue, it is necessary for them to enlist the aid of sociologists and psychologists working in universities. This is because the matter at hand is especially important.

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Structure should be provided by the government, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), academic institutions, and parents to reduce the negative effects on both physical and mental health. This can be done using regular routines, communication, and the formation of new partnerships. Learning at home has appeared as a practical alternative to the more conventional educational methods, and it should be maximized to offer children with the fundamental learning abilities they need at home while making the most use of the resources that are now accessible. Students can access remote resources from the comfort of their own homes to fulfill the requirements of the curriculum. When educating students via distance learning, one technique that instructors could use is to supply support for students' studying at home. Opportunities for the advancement of teacher quality and continued professional development should be supported throughout the whole of this transformation process. This should have priority position. It is important to get feedback from families to design a classroom setting that is beneficial to everyone. The tactics that have been mentioned above will result in disruptive innovations, which will need further testing for feasibility, quality control, and regulation in the system through which education is delivered.

Because of this, we are aware that children do best in environments that are consistent, and one of the most challenging aspects of the epidemic has been the fact that we have an extremely limited capacity to forecast what will occur next and how long it will take. Therefore, both families and educators can promote the well-being of children by setting regular routines that will continue to occur no matter what happens in the larger ecosystem of children's lives. As a result, it is a method for an adult to manage what happens to them, and self-talk can be an effective approach; one method is for an adult to create a model of management method for a carefully caring young child who is having some difficulties. It is possible for an adult to respond more harshly to children when they are going through a time of significant stress and frustration in their lives. This, in turn, may fuel the behavior of the kid. As the responsible adult, you must take a moment to stand back, halt, and address the burnout chain. Therefore, it is required that school administrators, psychologists and sociologists, academics, and parents continue to check these youngsters if they give us permission to do so. This responsibility applies to both academics and parents. We will be able to decide whether the changes we see are persistent over time if we use similar measures. This will be in addition to our ongoing efforts to understand how children's behavior and general well-being alter over the course of time. The other

thing that we are starting to do now is to go back to our families and help kids understand if we are seeing changes not only in social and emotional learning areas but also in more traditional academic areas, language development, literacy development, and how these are aligned with changes in children's behavioral health. We are doing this by going back to our families and helping kids understand if we are seeing changes not only in social and emotional learning areas but also in more traditional academic areas. involves talents. During the epidemic, some children's behaviors are negatively affected more than others, while other children's academic performance is negatively affected. Another topic that has been the focus of research is the question of how much genuine interest there is in finding connections between the experiences that children have in a variety of different domains and the experiences that families have in their orbits over the course of time. Therefore, it is necessary to try to supply information to educational systems as well as families.

11. References

- Al Lily AE, Ismail AF, Abunasser FM, Alqahtani RHA Distance education as a response to pandemics: coronavirus and Arab culture. Technol. Soc. 2020;63
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0160791X20303006>.
- "Alawamleh M., Al-Twait LM, Al-Saht GR The effect of online learning on communication between instructors and students during Covid-19 pandemic." ("Problematic Smartphone Use During the COVID-19 Pandemic") ("Zoom-based GROW coaching intervention for improving subjective well ...") Asian Educ. Giant. Stud. 2020;11(2):380 400.
- Alsobaie M. Hidden curriculum as one of current issue of curriculum. J Educ. practice 2015;6(33):125 128.
- Alsubaie M. Western Michigan University. Scholar Works; 2018. Ten Elementary School Teachers Voices: How They Build Effective Literacy Learning in the Lives of Their 2nd Grade Children.<https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/dissertations/3281> ("PREVIEW") ("PREVIEW")

Alsubaie, 2015 M. Alsubaie Hidden curriculum as one of current issue of curriculum J. Educ. Pract., 6 (33) (2015), pp. 125-128

ArticleDownload PDFView Record in Scopus Bol, 2020

Ay S.ç., Keskin HK, Akilli M. Examining the effects of negotiation and peer mediation on student's conflict resolution and critical thinking skills. int. J. Instruct. 2019;12(3):717 730.

Berker K. The effect of Covid-19 pandemic process on the speaking skill of children in distance education and daily life. Research Gate. 2021 <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/BerkerKurt/publication/352413905TheEffectofCovid19PandemicProcessonTheSpeakingSkillofChildreninDistanceEducationandDailyLife/links/60c8fb26a6fdcc0c5c865b-The-The-Effect-SkillofChildrenin-The-Effect-SkillofChildrenin-The-Effect-SkillofChildrenin-The-Effect-SkillofChildreninDistanceEducationandDailyLife/links/60c8fb26a6fdcc0c5c865bdren-The-Effect-Skillof-Chilli>

Distance-Education-and-Daily-Life.pdf

Berker, 2021 K. Berker The effect of Covid-19 pandemic process on the speaking skill of children in distance education and daily life Research Gate (2021) ("The Effect of Covid-19 Pandemic Process on The Speaking Skill of ...") ("The Effect of Covid-19 Pandemic Process on The Speaking Skill of ...") ("The Effect of Covid-19 Pandemic Process on The Speaking Skill of ...")

Blair C., McKinnon RD, Daneri MP Effect of the tools of the mind kindergarten program on children s social and emotional development. Early Child. pic. Q. 2018;43:52 61.

Blair et al., 2018 C. Blair, RD McKinnon, MP Daneri Effect of the tools of the mind kindergarten program on children s social and emotional development arly Child. pic. Q., 43 (2018), pp. 52-61

Bol T. 2020. Inequality in Homeschooling During the Corona Crisis in the Netherlands. First Results From the LISS Panel.

"Bond M. Schools and emergency remote education during the Covid-19

- pandemic: A living rapid systematic review." ("Medical teachers' experience of emergency remote teaching during the ...") ("Medical teachers' experience of emergency remote teaching during the ...") Asian J. Dist. Educ. 2020;15(2):191-247.
- Bond, 2020 M. Bond Schools and emergency remote education during the Covid-19 pandemic: A living rapid systematic review Asian J. Dist. Educ., 15 (2) (2020), pp. 191-247
- Bozkurt A., Sharma RC Emergency remote teaching in a time of global crisis due to CoronaVirus pandemic. Asian J. Dist. Educ. 2020;15(1):i-vi.
- Bozkurt and Sharma, 2020 A. Bozkurt, RC Sharma Emergency remote teaching in a time of global crisis due to CoronaVirus pandemic Asian J. Dist. Educ., 15 (1) (2020), pp. i-vi
- Bransen D., Govaerts MJ, Sluijsmans DM, Driessen EW Beyond the self: The role of co-regulation in medical students self-regulated learning. Med. Educ. 2020;54(3):234-241.
- Brina A., Delahunty D. Primary school education in the time of COVID-19 A literature review (Bachelor s Thesis, University of Oulu) 2021. <http://jultika.oulu.fi/files/nbnfioulu-202103241500.pdf>
- Burgess S., Sievertsen HH VoxEU; 2020. Schools, Skills, and Learning: The Impact of Covid-19 on Education. <https://voxeu.org/article/impact-covid-19-education>
- Chang HN, Osher D., Schanfield M., Sundius J., Bauer L. Attendance Works & American Institutes for Research (AIR); 2019. ("Distance education and the social literacy of elementary ... - Heliyon") Using Chronic Absence Data to Improve Conditions for Learning.
- Chilisa B., Preece J. Pearson Education; 2005. Research methods for adult educators in Africa.
- Coakley A. Peer mediation conflict management in a class of its own. J. Mediation Appl. Conflict Anal. 2019;6(2)
- Collins A., Halverson R. Teachers College Press; 2018. Rethinking Education in the Age of Technology: The Digital Revolution and Schooling in America.

- Coman C., Toru LG, Mesesan-Schmitz L., Stanciu C., Bularca MC Online teaching and learning in higher education during the coronavirus pandemic: students' perspective. sustainability. 2020;12(24):10367.
- Creswell J., Miller L. Deciding validity in qualitative inquiry. Theory Practice. 2000;39(3):124 130.
- Creswell JW Sage Publication, Inc.; 2009. Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches.
- Creswell JW Sage Publications, Inc.; 2013. Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches.
- D. Bransen, MJ Govaerts, DM Sluijsmans, EW Driessen
- Darling-Hammond L., Flook L., Cook-Harvey C., Barron B., Osher D. Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. Appl. Giant. sci. 2020;24(2):97 140.
- Dong C., Cao S., Li H. Young children s online learning during Covid-19 pandemic: Chinese parents' beliefs and attitudes. Child. Youth Serv. Rev. 2020;118:105440.
- Elliott V. Thinking about the coding process in qualitative data analysis. Qual. Rep. 2018;23(11):2850 2861.
- Falk B., Blumenreich M. Heinemann Press; 2005. The Power of Questions: A Guide to Teacher and Student Research. ("The power of questions : a guide to teacher and student research ...") ("9780325006987: The Power of Questions: A Guide to Teacher ... - AbeBooks")
- Ferri F., Grifoni P., Guzzo T. Online learning, and emergency remote teaching: opportunities and challenges in emergency situations. ("Presentación a distancia de tesis y trabajos finales de Posgrado ...") ("Perceived Barriers in Online Learning among Nursing Students during the ...") Societies. 2020;10(4):86.
- Fitria H., Maksum A., Kristiawan M. Covid-19 pandemic: Educational transformation at Paramount Elementary School Palembang. AL-ISHLAH: J. Pendidik. 2021;13(2):934 939.

- <http://journal.staihubbulwathan.id/index.php/alishlah/article/view/647/382>
- George DS, Strauss V., Meckler L., Heim J., Natanson H. The Washington Post; 2021. How The Pandemic is Reshaping Education. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/education/2021/03/15/pandemic-school-year-changes/>
- M. Alawamleh, LM Al-Twait, GR Al-Saht the effect of online learning on communication between instructors and students during Covid-19 pandemic Asian Educ. Giant. Stud., 11 (2) (2020), pp. 380-400
- M. Alsubaie Ten Elementary School Teachers Voices: How They Build Effective Literacy Learning in the Lives of Their 2nd Grade Children Western Michigan University. Scholar Works (2018)
- S.c. Ay, HK Keskin, M. Akilli Examining the effects of negotiation and peer mediation on student's conflict resolution and critical thinking skills Int. J. Instruct., 12 (3) (2019), pp. 717-730
- T. Bol Inequality in Homeschooling During the Corona Crisis in the Netherlands. First Results From the LISS Panel(2020)
- Teo TC, Divakar A. Understanding the concepts of digital learning approaches: An empirical analysis of schools in developing countries. J. Appl.Learn. teach. 2021;4(1):120 128.
- Tham JCK, Burnham KD, Hocutt DL, Ranade N., Misak J., Duin AH, Campbell JL Metaphors, mental models, and multiplicity: Understanding student feeling of digital literacy. Comput. comp. 2021;59:102628.
- Tyagi R., Vishwakarma S., Alexandrovich ZS, Mohammed S. Quality Education. ("Reducing Inequalities Through Education and Skill ... - SpringerLink") ("Distance education and the social literacy of elementary ... - Heliyon") 2020. ICT skills for sustainable development goal four; pp. 435 442.
- Tzifopoulos M. In the shadow of Coronavirus: distance education and digital literacy skills in Greece. int. J. Soc. sci. Technol. 2020;5(2):1 14. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341358736TzifopoulosM2020IntheshadowofCoronavirusDistanceeducationanddigitalliteracyskillsinGreece.Inte>

- International Journal of Social Science and Technology 521–14
- UNESCO . 2020. Covid-19 Educational Disruption and Response.
- Uzun EM, Kar EB, Ozdemir Y. Examining first-grade teachers experiences and approaches about the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on teaching and learning. (“Examining first-grade teachers’ experiences and approaches regarding ...”) (“Examining first-grade teachers' experiences and approaches ...”) Educ. Process: Int. J. 2021;10(3):13 38. <http://www.edupij.com/files/1/articles/article226/EDUPIJ226article60ee3f91db48d.pdf>
- Vedder-Weiss D., Segal A., Lefstein A. Teacher face-work in discussions of video-recorded classroom practice: Constraining or catalyzing opportunities to gain experience? (“Teacher Face-Work in Discussions of Video-Recorded Classroom Practice ...”) (“Appendix_F_JTE841895 – Supplemental material for Teacher Face ... - CORE”) J. Teach. Educ. 2019;70(5):538 551.
- Vindrola-Padros C., Chisnall G., Cooper S., Dowrick A., Djellouli N., Symmons SM, Johnson GA Conducting rapid qualitative research during a pandemic: Emerging lessons from Covid 19. Qual. Health Res. 2020;30(14):2192 2204.
- Wang P., Wu P., Wang J., Chi HL, Wang X. A critical review of the use of virtual reality in construction engineering education and training. int. J. Environ. pic. Publ. health. 2018;15(6):1204.
- Wright TS, Domke LM The role of language and literacy in K-5 science and social studies standards. J. Literacy Res. 2019;51(1):5 29.
- Yan L., Whitelock-Wainwright A., Guan Q., Wen G., Gaaevi D., Chen G. Students experience of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic: a province-wide survey study. (“Students’ experience of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: a ...”) (“Students' experience of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: a ...”) Br. J Educ. Technol. 2021:2038 2057.
- Yang X., Zhang M., Kong L., Wang Q., Hong JC The effects of scientific self-efficacy

CURRENT SCIENCE

and cognitive anxiety on science engagement with the question-observation-doing-explanation model during school disruption in Covid-19 pandemic. J. Sci. Educ. Technol. 2021;30(3):380 393.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10956-020-09877-x>